

On Some Characterization of Ruled Surface of a Closed Spacelike Curve with Spacelike Binormal in Dual Lorentzian Space

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Abstract: In this paper, we investigate the relations between the pitch, the angle of pitch and drall of parallel ruled surface of a closed spacelike curve with spacelike binormal in dual Lorentzian space.

Key Words: Spacelike dual curve, ruled surface, Lorentzian space, dual numbers.

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§1. Introduction

Dual numbers were introduced by W.K. Clifford [5] as a tool for his geometrical investigations. After him, E. Study used dual numbers and dual vectors in his research on the geometry of lines and kinematics [7]. The pitches and the angles of the pitches of the closed ruled surfaces corresponding to the one parameter dual unit spherical curves and oriented lines in \mathbb{R}^3 were calculated respectively by Hacısalihoğlu [10] and Gürsoy [8]. Definitions of the parallel ruled surface were presented by Wilhelm Blaschke [6]. The integral invariants of the parallel ruled surfaces in the 3-dimensional Euclidean space \mathbb{R}^3 corresponding to the unit dual spherical parallel curves were calculated by Senyurt [14]. The integral invariants of ruled surface of a timelike curve in dual Lorentzian space were calculated by Bektaş and Şenyurt [2]. The integral invariants of ruled surface of a closed spacelike curve with timelike binormal in dual Lorentzian space were calculated by Bektaş and Şenyurt [3].

The set $D = \{\hat{\lambda} = \lambda + \varepsilon\lambda^* | \lambda, \lambda^* \in \mathbb{R}, \varepsilon^2 = 0\}$ is called *dual numbers* set, see [5]. On this set, product and addition operations are respectively

$$(\lambda + \varepsilon\lambda^*) + (\beta + \varepsilon\beta^*) = (\lambda + \beta) + \varepsilon(\lambda^* + \beta^*)$$

and

$$(\lambda + \varepsilon\lambda^*)(\beta + \varepsilon\beta^*) = \lambda\beta + \varepsilon(\lambda\beta^* + \lambda^*\beta).$$

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The elements of the set $D^3 = \left\{ \vec{A} = \vec{a} + \varepsilon \vec{a}^* \mid \vec{a}, \vec{a}^* \in \mathbb{R}^3 \right\}$ are called *dual vectors*. On this set addition and scalar product operations are respectively

$$\oplus : D^3 \times D^3 \rightarrow D^3$$

$$\left(\vec{A}, \vec{B} \right) \rightarrow \vec{A} \oplus \vec{B} = \vec{a} + \vec{b} + \varepsilon \left(\vec{a}^* + \vec{b}^* \right),$$

$$\odot : D \times D^3 \rightarrow D^3$$

$$\left(\lambda, \vec{A} \right) \rightarrow \lambda \odot \vec{A} = (\lambda + \varepsilon \lambda^*) \odot (\vec{a} + \varepsilon \vec{a}^*) = \lambda \vec{a} + \varepsilon (\lambda \vec{a}^* + \lambda^* \vec{a})$$

The set (D^3, \oplus) is a module over the ring $(D, +, \cdot)$, called the *D-Modul*.

The Lorentzian inner product of dual vectors $\vec{A}, \vec{B} \in D^3$ is defined by

$$\langle \vec{A}, \vec{B} \rangle = \langle \vec{a}, \vec{b} \rangle + \varepsilon \left(\langle \vec{a}, \vec{b}^* \rangle + \langle \vec{a}^*, \vec{b} \rangle \right)$$

where $\langle \vec{a}, \vec{b} \rangle$ is the following Lorentzian inner product of vectors $\vec{a} = (a_1, a_2, a_3)$ and $\vec{b} = (b_1, b_2, b_3) \in \mathbb{R}^3$, i.e.,

$$\langle \vec{a}, \vec{b} \rangle = -a_1 b_1 + a_2 b_2 + a_3 b_3.$$

The set D^3 equipped with the Lorentzian inner product $\langle \vec{A}, \vec{B} \rangle$ is called 3-dimensional dual Lorentzian space and is denoted in what follows by $D_1^3 = \left\{ \vec{A} = \vec{a} + \varepsilon \vec{a}^* \mid \vec{a}, \vec{a}^* \in \mathbb{R}^3 \right\}$ [17].

A dual vector $\vec{A} = \vec{a} + \varepsilon \vec{a}^* \in D_1^3$ is called dual space-like vector if $\langle \vec{A}, \vec{A} \rangle > 0$ or $\vec{A} = 0$, a dual time-like vector if $\langle \vec{A}, \vec{A} \rangle < 0$, a dual null (light-like) vector if $\langle \vec{A}, \vec{A} \rangle = 0$ for $\vec{A} \neq 0$. For $\vec{A} \neq 0$, the *norm* $\|\vec{A}\|$ of \vec{A} is defined by

$$\|\vec{A}\| = \sqrt{|\langle \vec{A}, \vec{A} \rangle|} = \|\vec{a}\| + \varepsilon \frac{\langle \vec{a}, \vec{a}^* \rangle}{\|\vec{a}\|}, \quad \|\vec{a}\| \neq 0.$$

The dual Lorentzian cross-product of $\vec{A}, \vec{B} \in D^3$ is defined as

$$\vec{A} \wedge \vec{B} = \vec{a} \times \vec{b} + \varepsilon \left(\vec{a} \times \vec{b}^* + \vec{a}^* \times \vec{b} \right)$$

where $\vec{a} \times \vec{b}$ is the cross-product [14] of $\vec{a}, \vec{b} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ given by

$$\vec{a} \times \vec{b} = (a_3 b_2 - a_2 b_3, a_1 b_3 - a_3 b_1, a_1 b_2 - a_2 b_1).$$

Theorem 1.1(E. Study) *The oriented lines in \mathbb{R}^3 are in one to one correspondence with the points of the dual unit sphere $\|\vec{A}\| = (1, 0)$ where $\vec{A} \neq (\vec{0}, \vec{a}) \in D\text{-Modul}$, see [9].*

The dual number $\Phi = \varphi + \varepsilon \varphi^*$ is called dual angle between the unit dual vectors \vec{A} ve \vec{B} and keep in mind that

$$\begin{aligned} \sin(\varphi + \varepsilon \varphi^*) &= \sin \varphi + \varepsilon \varphi^* \cos \varphi, \\ \cos(\varphi + \varepsilon \varphi^*) &= \cos \varphi - \varepsilon \varphi^* \sin \varphi. \end{aligned}$$

§2. Characterization of Ruled Surface of a Closed Spacelike Curve with Spacelike Binormal in Dual Lorentzian Space (D_1^3)

Let $U : I \rightarrow D_1^3$, $t \rightarrow \vec{U}(t) = \vec{U}_1(t)$, $\|\vec{U}(t)\| = 1$ be a differentiable spacelike curve with spacelike binormal in the dual unit sphere. Denote by (\vec{U}) the closed ruled generated by this curve.

Let $\{\vec{U}_1, \vec{U}_2, \vec{U}_3\}$ be the Frenet frame of the curve $\vec{U} = \vec{U}_1$ with

$$\vec{U}_1 = \vec{U}, \quad \vec{U}_2 = \vec{U}' / \|\vec{U}'\|, \quad \vec{U}_3 = \vec{U}_1 \times \vec{U}_2$$

Definition 2.1 The closed ruled surface (\vec{V}) corresponding to the dual spacelike curve $\vec{U}(t)$ which makes the fixed dual angle $\Phi = \varphi + \varepsilon\varphi^*$ with $\vec{U}(t)$ determines

$$\vec{V} = \cos \Phi \vec{U}_1 + \sin \Phi \vec{U}_3 \quad (2.1)$$

The surface (\vec{V}) corresponding to the dual spacelike vector \vec{V} is called the *parallel ruled surface* of surface (\vec{U}) in the dual Lorentzian space D_1^3 .

Now, take $\vec{U}(t)$ as a closed spacelike curve with curvature $\kappa = k_1 + \varepsilon k_1^*$ and torsion $\tau = k_2 + \varepsilon k_2^*$. Recall that in the Frenet frames associated to the curve \vec{U}_1 and \vec{U}_3 are spacelike vectors and \vec{U}_2 is timelike vector and we have

$$\vec{U}_1 \times \vec{U}_2 = -\vec{U}_3, \quad \vec{U}_2 \times \vec{U}_3 = -\vec{U}_1, \quad \vec{U}_3 \times \vec{U}_1 = \vec{U}_2. \quad (2.2)$$

Under these conditions, the Frenet formulas are given by ([18])

$$\vec{U}_1' = \kappa \vec{U}_2, \quad \vec{U}_2' = \kappa \vec{U}_1 + \tau \vec{U}_3, \quad \vec{U}_3' = \tau \vec{U}_2. \quad (2.3)$$

The Frenet instantaneous rotation vector (also called instantaneous Darboux vector) for the spacelike curve is given by ([16])

$$\vec{\Psi} = -\tau \vec{U}_1 + \kappa \vec{U}_3, \quad (2.4)$$

Let be $\vec{V}_1 = \vec{V}$. Differentiating of the vector \vec{V}_1 with respect the parameter t and using the Eq.(2.3) we get

$$\vec{V}_1' = (\kappa \cos \Phi + \tau \sin \Phi) \vec{U}_2 \quad (2.5)$$

and the norm of that vector denoted by P is

$$P = \kappa \cos \Phi + \tau \sin \Phi. \quad (2.6)$$

Then, substituting the values of (2.5) and (2.6) into Frenet equations gives

$$\vec{V}_2 = \vec{U}_2 \quad (2.7)$$

For the vector \vec{V}_3 , we have

$$\vec{V}_3 = \sin \Phi \vec{U}_1 - \cos \Phi \vec{U}_3 \quad (2.8)$$

If Eq.(2.1), (2.7) and (2.8) are written matrix form, we have

$$\begin{bmatrix} \vec{V}_1 \\ \vec{V}_2 \\ \vec{V}_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \Phi & 0 & \sin \Phi \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ \sin \Phi & 0 & -\cos \Phi \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \vec{U}_1 \\ \vec{U}_2 \\ \vec{U}_3 \end{bmatrix}$$

or

$$\begin{bmatrix} \vec{U}_1 \\ \vec{U}_2 \\ \vec{U}_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \Phi & 0 & \sin \Phi \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ \sin \Phi & 0 & -\cos \Phi \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \vec{V}_1 \\ \vec{V}_2 \\ \vec{V}_3 \end{bmatrix}$$

The real and dual parts of $\vec{U}_1, \vec{U}_2, \vec{U}_3$ are

$$\begin{cases} \vec{u}_1 = \cos \varphi \vec{v}_1 + \sin \varphi \vec{v}_3 \\ \vec{u}_2 = \vec{v}_2 \\ \vec{u}_3 = \sin \varphi \vec{v}_1 - \cos \varphi \vec{v}_3 \\ \vec{u}_1^* = \cos \varphi \vec{v}_1^* + \sin \varphi \vec{v}_3^* - \varphi^* (\sin \varphi \vec{v}_1 - \cos \varphi \vec{v}_3) \\ \vec{u}_2^* = \vec{v}_2^* \\ \vec{u}_3^* = \sin \varphi \vec{v}_1^* - \cos \varphi \vec{v}_3^* + \varphi^* (\cos \varphi \vec{v}_1 - \sin \varphi \vec{v}_3) \end{cases} \quad (2.9)$$

Let $P = p + \varepsilon p^*$ be the curvature and $Q = q + \varepsilon q^*$ the torsion of curve $\vec{V}(t)$. Then, the following relating holds between the vectors

$$\vec{V}_1, \vec{V}_2, \vec{V}_3 \text{ and } \vec{V}_1', \vec{V}_2', \vec{V}_3' \quad [18]$$

$$\begin{cases} \vec{V}_1' = P\vec{V}_2, \quad \vec{V}_2' = P\vec{V}_1 + Q\vec{V}_3, \quad \vec{V}_3' = Q\vec{V}_2 \\ P = \sqrt{\langle \vec{V}_1', \vec{V}_1' \rangle}, \quad Q = \frac{\det(\vec{V}_1, \vec{V}_1', \vec{V}_1'')}{\langle \vec{V}_1, \vec{V}_1 \rangle} \end{cases} \quad (2.10)$$

If Eq.(2.10) is separated into its real and dual parts, we get

$$\begin{cases} \vec{v}_1' = p\vec{v}_2, \quad \vec{v}_2' = p\vec{v}_1 + q\vec{v}_3, \quad \vec{v}_3' = q\vec{v}_2 \\ \vec{v}_1'^* = p\vec{v}_2^* + p^*\vec{v}_2, \\ \vec{v}_2'^* = p\vec{v}_1^* + p^*\vec{v}_1 + q^*\vec{v}_3 + q\vec{v}_3^*, \\ \vec{v}_3'^* = q\vec{v}_2^* + q^*\vec{v}_2 \end{cases} \quad (2.11)$$

Now, we are ready to calculate the value of Q as function of κ and τ . Differentiating Eq.(2.5) with respect to the curve parameter t we get

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{V}_1'' &= (+\kappa^2 \cos \Phi + \kappa\tau \sin \Phi) \vec{U}_1 + \\ &+ (\kappa \cos \Phi + \tau \sin \Phi)' \vec{U}_2 + (\kappa\tau \cos \Phi + \tau^2 \sin \Phi) \vec{U}_3 \end{aligned} \quad (2.12)$$

Using Eqs.(2.1), (2.5) and (2.12) into Eq.(2.10), we get

$$Q = -\kappa \sin \Phi + \tau \cos \Phi \quad (2.13)$$

and separating Eq.(2.6) and Eq.(2.13) into its dual and real parts gives

$$\begin{cases} p = k_1 \cos \varphi + k_2 \sin \varphi \\ p^* = k_1^* \cos \varphi + k_2^* \sin \varphi - \varphi^* (k_1 \sin \varphi - k_2 \cos \varphi) \\ q = -k_1 \sin \varphi + k_2 \cos \varphi \\ q^* = -k_1^* \sin \varphi + k_2^* \cos \varphi - \varphi^* (k_1 \cos \varphi + k_2 \sin \varphi) \end{cases} \quad (2.14)$$

In its dual unit spherical motion the dual orthonormal system $\{\vec{V}_1, \vec{V}_2, \vec{V}_3\}$ at any t makes a dual rotation motion around the instantaneous dual Darboux vector. This vector is determined by the following equation ([16]).

$$\vec{\Psi} = -Q\vec{V}_1 + P\vec{V}_3. \quad (2.15)$$

For the Steiner vector of the motion, we can write

$$\vec{D} = \oint \vec{\Psi} \quad (2.16)$$

or

$$\vec{D} = -\vec{V}_1 \oint Q dt + \vec{V}_3 \oint P dt \quad (2.17)$$

Using the values of the vectors \vec{U}_1 and \vec{U}_3 into Eq.(2.4), gives

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{\Psi} &= -\tau(\cos\Phi\vec{V}_1 + \sin\Phi\vec{V}_3) + \kappa(\sin\Phi\vec{V}_1 - \cos\Phi\vec{V}_3), \\ \vec{\Psi} &= -Q\vec{V}_1 - P\vec{V}_3 \end{aligned} \quad (2.18)$$

Because of the equations $\vec{D} = \oint \vec{\Psi}$ for the dual Steiner vector of the motion, we may write

$$\vec{D} = -\vec{V}_1 \oint Q dt - \vec{V}_3 \oint P dt \quad (2.19)$$

The real and dual parts of \vec{D} are

$$\begin{cases} \vec{d} = -\vec{v}_1 \oint q dt - \vec{v}_3 \oint p dt, \\ \vec{d}^* = -\vec{v}_1 \oint q^* dt - \vec{v}_1^* \oint q dt - \vec{v}_3 \oint p^* dt - \vec{v}_3^* \oint p dt \end{cases} \quad (2.20)$$

$$\vec{D} = -\vec{U}_1 \oint \tau dt + \vec{U}_3 \oint \kappa dt \quad (2.21)$$

Eq.(2.21) can be written type of the dual and real part as follow

$$\begin{cases} \vec{d} = -\vec{u}_1 \oint k_2 dt + \vec{u}_3 \oint k_1 dt, \\ \vec{d}^* = -\vec{u}_1^* \oint k_2 dt - \vec{u}_1 \oint k_2^* dt + \vec{u}_3^* \oint k_1 dt + \vec{u}_3 \oint k_1^* dt \end{cases} \quad (2.22)$$

If the equation (2.3) is separated into the dual and real part, we can obtain

$$\begin{cases} \vec{u}'_1 = k_1 \vec{u}_2, \quad \vec{u}'_2 = k_1 \vec{u}_1 + k_2 \vec{u}_3, \quad \vec{u}'_3 = k_2 \vec{u}_2 \\ \vec{u}'_1{}^* = k_1^* \vec{u}_2 + k_1 \vec{u}_2^*, \\ \vec{u}'_2{}^* = k_1^* \vec{u}_1 + k_2^* \vec{u}_3 + k_1 \vec{u}_1^* + k_2 \vec{u}_3^* \\ \vec{u}'_3{}^* = k_2^* \vec{u}_2 + k_2 \vec{u}_2^* \end{cases} \quad (2.23)$$

Now, let us calculate the integral invariants of the respective closed ruled surfaces. The pitch of the first closed surface (U_1) is obtained as

$$\begin{aligned} L_{u_1} &= \left\langle \vec{d}, \vec{u}_1^* \right\rangle + \left\langle \vec{d}^*, \vec{u}_1 \right\rangle, \\ L_{u_1} &= - \oint k_2^* dt. \end{aligned} \quad (2.24)$$

The dual angle of the pitch of the closed surface U_1 is

$$\Lambda_{U_1} = - \left\langle \vec{D}, \vec{U}_1 \right\rangle.$$

and from Eq.(2.21) we obtain

$$\Lambda_{U_1} = \oint \tau dt. \quad (2.25)$$

The real and dual of U_1 are

$$\lambda_{u_1} = \oint k_2 dt \quad , \quad L_{u_1} = - \oint k_2^* dt \quad (2.26)$$

The *drall* of the closed surface (U_1) is

$$P_{U_1} = \frac{\langle d\vec{u}_1, d\vec{u}_1^* \rangle}{\langle d\vec{u}_1, d\vec{u}_1 \rangle}$$

Using the values $d\vec{u}_1$ and $d\vec{u}_1^*$ given by Eq.(2.23), we get

$$P_{U_1} = \frac{k_1^*}{k_1} \quad (2.27)$$

The pitch of the closed surface (U_2) is given by

$$L_{u_2} = 0. \quad (2.28)$$

The dual angle of the pitch of the closed surface (U_2) is

$$\begin{aligned} \Lambda_{U_2} &= - \left\langle \vec{D}, \vec{U}_2 \right\rangle, \\ \Lambda_{U_2} &= 0. \end{aligned} \quad (2.29)$$

The *drall* of the closed surface (U_2), we may write

$$P_{U_2} = \frac{\langle d\vec{u}_2, d\vec{u}_2^* \rangle}{\langle d\vec{u}_2, d\vec{u}_2 \rangle}$$

Using the values $d\vec{u}_2$ and $d\vec{u}_2^*$ given by Eq.(2.23), we get

$$P_{U_2} = \frac{k_1 k_1^* + k_2 k_2^*}{k_1^2 + k_2^2} \quad (2.30)$$

The pitch of the closed surface (U_3) is

$$L_{u_3} = \left\langle \vec{d}, \vec{u}_3^* \right\rangle + \left\langle \vec{d}^*, \vec{u}_3 \right\rangle,$$

$$L_{u_3} = \oint k_1^* dt \quad (2.31)$$

The dual angle of the pitch of the closed surface (U_3) is

$$\Lambda_{U_3} = - \left\langle \vec{D}, \vec{U}_3 \right\rangle$$

which gives using (2.21)

$$\Lambda_{U_3} = - \oint \kappa dt \quad (2.32)$$

The real and dual parts of Λ_{U_3} are

$$\lambda_{u_3} = - \oint k_1 dt \quad , \quad L_{u_3} = \oint k_1^* dt \quad (2.33)$$

The drall of the closed surface (U_3) is

$$P_{U_3} = \frac{\langle d\vec{u}_3, d\vec{u}_3^* \rangle}{\langle d\vec{u}_3, d\vec{u}_3 \rangle}$$

Using the values of $d\vec{u}_3$ and $d\vec{u}_3^*$ given in Eq.(2.23) gives

$$P_{U_3} = \frac{k_2^*}{k_2}. \quad (2.34)$$

Let $\Omega(t) = \omega(t) + \varepsilon\omega^*(t)$ be the Lorentzian timelike angle between the instantaneous dual Pfaffion vector $\vec{\Psi}$ and the vector \vec{U}_3 . In this case dual Pfaffion vector $\vec{\Psi}$ is spacelike vector and so,

$$\kappa = \left\| \vec{\Psi} \right\| \cos \Omega \quad , \quad \tau = \left\| \vec{\Psi} \right\| \sin \Omega$$

then $\vec{C} = \vec{c} + \varepsilon \vec{c}^*$, the unit vector in the $\vec{\Psi}$ direction is

$$\vec{C} = - \sin \Omega \vec{U}_1 + \cos \Omega \vec{U}_3 \quad (2.35)$$

and the real and dual parts of \vec{C} are

$$\begin{cases} \vec{c} = - \sin \omega \vec{u}_1 + \cos \omega \vec{u}_3 \\ \vec{c}^* = - \sin \omega \vec{u}_1^* + \cos \omega \vec{u}_3^* - \omega^* \cos \omega \vec{u}_1 - \omega^* \sin \omega \vec{u}_3 \end{cases} \quad (2.36)$$

The pitch of the closed surface (\vec{C}) generated by \vec{C} is given by

$$L_C = \langle \vec{d}, \vec{c}^* \rangle + \langle \vec{d}^*, \vec{c} \rangle$$

$$L_C = \cos \omega \oint k_1^* dt + \sin \omega \oint k_2^* dt - \omega^* (\sin \omega \oint k_1 dt - \cos \omega \oint k_2 dt) \quad (2.37)$$

If we use Eq.(2.26) and Eq.(2.33) into Eq.(2.37) we get

$$L_C = - \sin \omega L_{u_1} + \cos \omega L_{u_3} + \omega^* (\cos \omega \lambda_{u_1} + \sin \omega \lambda_{u_3}) \quad (2.38)$$

The dual angle of the pitch of that closed ruled surface (\vec{C}), we have

$$\Lambda_C = - \left\langle \vec{D}, \vec{C} \right\rangle$$

and from Eq.(2.21) and (2.35) it follows that

$$\begin{aligned}\Lambda_{U_3} &= - \langle \vec{U}_1 \oint \tau dt + \vec{U}_3 \oint \kappa dt, -\sin \Omega \vec{U}_1 + \cos \Omega \vec{U}_3 \rangle, \\ \Lambda_C &= -\sin \Omega \oint \tau dt - \cos \Omega \oint \kappa dt\end{aligned}\quad (2.39)$$

Using Eg.(2.25) and (2.32) gives

$$\Lambda_C = -\sin \Omega \Lambda_{U_1} + \cos \Omega \Lambda_{U_3} \quad (2.40)$$

The drall of the closed surface (\vec{C}) is

$$\begin{aligned}P_C &= \frac{\langle d\vec{c}, d\vec{c}^* \rangle}{\langle d\vec{c}, d\vec{c} \rangle} \\ P_C &= \frac{\omega' \omega^* - (k_2 \cos \omega - k_1 \sin \omega) [(k_2^* - k_1 \omega^*) \cos \omega - (k_2 \omega^* + k_1^*) \sin \omega]}{\omega'^2 - (k_2 \cos \omega - k_1 \sin \omega)^2}\end{aligned}\quad (2.41)$$

Now, let us calculate the integral invariants of the respective closed ruled surfaces. The pitch of the closed (V_1) surface is given by

$$\begin{aligned}L_{V_1} &= \langle \vec{d}, \vec{v}_1^* \rangle + \langle \vec{d}^*, \vec{v}_1 \rangle, \\ L_{V_1} &= - \oint q^* dt.\end{aligned}\quad (2.42)$$

Substituting by the value q^* into Eq.(2.42)

$$L_{V_1} = \sin \varphi \oint k_1^* dt - \cos \varphi \oint k_2^* dt + \varphi^* (\cos \varphi \oint k_1 dt + \sin \varphi \oint k_2 dt) \quad (2.43)$$

or

$$L_{V_1} = \cos \varphi L_{u_1} + \sin \varphi L_{u_3} + \varphi^* (\sin \varphi \lambda_{u_1} - \cos \varphi \lambda_{u_3}). \quad (2.44)$$

The dual angle of the pitch of the closed ruled surface (V_1) , we have

$$\Lambda_{V_1} = - \langle \vec{D}, \vec{V}_1 \rangle$$

and using Eq.(2.19) we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}\Lambda_{V_1} &= - \langle -\vec{V}_1 \oint Q dt - \vec{V}_3 \oint P dt, \vec{V}_1 \rangle, \\ \Lambda_{V_1} &= \oint Q dt.\end{aligned}\quad (2.45)$$

Using Eq.(2.13) into the last equation, we get

$$\Lambda_{V_1} = -\sin \Phi \oint \kappa dt + \cos \Phi \oint \tau dt$$

or

$$\Lambda_{V_1} = \cos \Phi \Lambda_{U_1} + \sin \Phi \Lambda_{U_3} \quad (2.46)$$

Separating Eq.(2.46) into its real and dual parts gives

$$\begin{cases} \lambda_{V_1} = \cos \varphi \lambda_{u_1} + \sin \varphi \lambda_{u_3} \\ L_{V_1} = \cos \varphi L_{u_1} + \sin \varphi L_{u_3} + \varphi^* (\sin \varphi \lambda_{u_1} - \cos \varphi \lambda_{u_3}) \end{cases} \quad (2.47)$$

The drall of the closed surface (V_1) is

$$P_{V_1} = \frac{\langle d\vec{v}_1, d\vec{v}_1^* \rangle}{\langle d\vec{v}_1, d\vec{v}_1 \rangle}$$

which gives using the values of $d\vec{v}_1$ and $d\vec{v}_1^*$ in Eq.(2.11)

$$P_{V_1} = \frac{p^*}{p} \quad (2.48)$$

and using the values of p and p^* given by Eq.(2.14) gives

$$P_{V_1} = \frac{k_1^* \cos \varphi + k_2^* \sin \varphi}{k_1 \cos \varphi + k_2 \sin \varphi} - \varphi^* \frac{k_1 \sin \varphi - k_2 \cos \varphi}{k_1 \cos \varphi + k_2 \sin \varphi} \quad (2.49)$$

Theorem 2.1 *Let (V_1) be the parallel surface of the surface (U_1). The pitch, drall and the dual of the pitch of the ruled surface (V_1) are*

$$1-) L_{V_1} = - \oint q^* dt \quad 2-) \Lambda_{V_1} = \oint Q dt \quad 3-) P_{V_1} = \frac{p^*}{p}$$

Corollary 2.1 *Let (V_1) be the parallel surface of the surface (U_1). The pitch and the dual of the pitch of the ruled surface (V_1) related to the invariants of the surface (U_1) are written as follow*

$$\begin{aligned} 1-) L_{V_1} &= \cos \varphi L_{u_1} + \sin \varphi L_{u_3} + \varphi^* (\sin \varphi \lambda_{u_1} - \cos \varphi \lambda_{u_3}); \\ 2-) \Lambda_{V_1} &= \cos \Phi \Lambda_{U_1} + \sin \Phi \Lambda_{U_3} \end{aligned}$$

The pitch of the closed surface (V_2) is given by

$$\begin{aligned} L_{V_2} &= \langle \vec{d}, \vec{v}_2^* \rangle + \langle \vec{d}^*, \vec{v}_2 \rangle \\ L_{V_2} &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (2.50)$$

The dual angle of the pitch of the closed ruled surface (V_2) is

$$\Lambda_{V_2} = - \langle \vec{D}, \vec{V}_2 \rangle$$

Using Eq.(2.19) we get

$$\Lambda_{V_2} = 0 \quad (2.51)$$

The drall of the closed surface (V_2) is

$$P_{V_2} = \frac{\langle d\vec{v}_2, d\vec{v}_2^* \rangle}{\langle d\vec{v}_2, d\vec{v}_2 \rangle}$$

Using the values of \vec{dv}_2 and \vec{dv}_2^* given by Eq.(2.11) gives

$$P_{V_2} = \frac{pp^* + qq^*}{p^2 + q^2} \quad (2.52)$$

and with the values of p, p^*, q and q^* given by Eq.(2.14) we get

$$P_{V_2} = \frac{k_1 k_1^* + k_2 k_2^*}{k_1^2 + k_2^2} \quad (2.53)$$

Theorem 2.2 *Let (V_1) be the parallel surface of the surface (U_1) . The pitch, drall and the dual of the pitch of the ruled surface (V_2) are*

$$1-)L_{V_2} = 0 \quad 2-)\Lambda_{V_2} = 0 \quad 3-)P_{V_2} = \frac{pp^* + qq^*}{p^2 + q^2}$$

The pitch of the closed surface (V_3) is given by

$$\begin{aligned} L_{V_3} &= \langle \vec{d}, \vec{v}_3^* \rangle + \langle \vec{d}^*, \vec{v}_3 \rangle, \\ L_{V_3} &= - \oint p^* dt \end{aligned} \quad (2.54)$$

and using Eq.(2.54)

$$L_{V_3} = -\cos \varphi \oint k_1^* dt - \sin \varphi \oint k_2^* dt + \varphi^* (\sin \varphi \oint k_1 dt - \cos \varphi \oint k_2 dt) \quad (2.55)$$

or

$$L_{V_3} = \sin \varphi L_{u_1} - \cos \varphi L_{u_3} - \varphi^* (\cos \varphi \lambda_{u_1} + \sin \varphi \lambda_{u_3}) \quad (2.56)$$

The dual angle of the pitch of the closed ruled surface (V_3) is

$$\Lambda_{V_3} = - \langle \vec{D}, \vec{V}_3 \rangle$$

Due to Eq.(2.19) we have

$$\begin{aligned} \Lambda_{V_3} &= - \langle \vec{V}_1 \oint Q dt - \vec{V}_3 \oint P dt, \vec{V}_3 \rangle, \\ \Lambda_{V_3} &= \oint P dt. \end{aligned} \quad (2.57)$$

and using Eq.(2.6) into the last equation gives

$$\Lambda_{V_3} = \cos \Phi \oint \kappa dt + \sin \Phi \oint \tau dt$$

or

$$\Lambda_{V_3} = \sin \Phi \Lambda_{U_1} - \cos \Phi \Lambda_{U_3} \quad (2.58)$$

Separating Eq.(2.58) into its real and dual parts give

$$\begin{cases} \lambda_{v_3} = \sin \varphi \lambda_{u_1} - \cos \varphi \lambda_{u_3} \\ L_{v_3} = \sin \varphi L_{u_1} - \cos \varphi L_{u_3} - \varphi^* (\cos \varphi \lambda_{u_1} + \sin \varphi \lambda_{u_3}) \end{cases} \quad (2.59)$$

The drall of the closed surface (V_3) is

$$P_{V_3} = \frac{\langle d\vec{v}_3, d\vec{v}_3^* \rangle}{\langle d\vec{v}_3, d\vec{v}_3 \rangle}$$

Using the values of $d\vec{v}_3$ and $d\vec{v}_3^*$ given by Eq.(2.11) gives

$$P_{V_3} = \frac{q^*}{q} \quad (2.60)$$

and using the values of q and q^* given by Eq.(2.14) into the last equations, we get

$$P_{V_3} = \frac{-k_1^* \sin \varphi - k_2^* \cos \varphi}{-k_1 \sin \varphi + k_2 \cos \varphi} - \varphi^* \left(\frac{k_1 \cos \varphi + k_2 \sin \varphi}{-k_1 \sin \varphi + k_2 \cos \varphi} \right) \quad (2.61)$$

Theorem 2.3 *Let (V_1) be the parallel surface of the surface (U_1). The pitch, drall and the dual of the pitch of the ruled surface (V_3) are*

$$1-) L_{V_3} = - \oint p^* dt \quad 2-) \Lambda_{V_3} = \oint P dt \quad 3-) P_{V_3} = \frac{q^*}{q}.$$

Corollary 2.2 *Let (V_1) be the parallel surface of the surface (U_1). The pitch and the dual of the pitch of the ruled surface (V_3) related to the invariants of the surface (U_1) are written as follow*

$$1-) L_{V_3} = \sin \varphi L_{u_1} - \cos \varphi L_{u_3} - \varphi^* (\cos \varphi \lambda_{u_1} + \sin \varphi \lambda_{u_3});$$

$$2-) \Lambda_{V_3} = \sin \Phi \Lambda_{U_1} - \cos \Phi \Lambda_{U_3}.$$

Let $\Theta(t) = \theta(t) + \varepsilon \theta^*(t)$ be the Lorentzian timelike angle between the instantaneous dual Pfaffion vector $\vec{\Psi}$ and the vector \vec{V}_3 .

In this case dual Pfaffion vector $\vec{\Psi}$ is spacelike vector,

$$P = \left\| \vec{\Psi} \right\| \cos \Theta, \quad Q = \left\| \vec{\Psi} \right\| \sin \Theta$$

The unit vector $\vec{C} = \vec{c} + \varepsilon \vec{c}^*$, in the $\vec{\Psi}$ direction is

$$\vec{C} = -\sin \Theta \vec{V}_1 + \cos \Theta \vec{V}_3 \quad (2.62)$$

Using the values of the vectors \vec{V}_1 and \vec{V}_3 given by Eq.(2.9) into Eq.(2.62), we get

$$\vec{C} = -\sin \Theta \left(\cos \Phi \vec{U}_1 + \sin \Phi \vec{U}_3 \right) + \cos \Theta \left(\sin \Phi \vec{U}_1 - \cos \Phi \vec{U}_3 \right)$$

$$\vec{C} = \sin(\Theta - \Phi) \vec{U}_1 - \cos(\Theta - \Phi) \vec{U}_3 \quad (2.63)$$

The real and dual parts of \vec{C} are

$$\begin{cases} \vec{c} = -\sin \theta \vec{v}_1 + \cos \theta \vec{v}_3 \\ \vec{c}^* = -\sin \theta \vec{v}_1^* + \cos \theta \vec{v}_3^* - \theta^* \cos \theta \vec{v}_1 - \theta^* \sin \theta \vec{v}_3 \end{cases} \quad (2.64)$$

The pitch of the closed surface (\vec{C}) is given by

$$L_{\vec{C}} = \langle \vec{d}, \vec{c}^* \rangle + \langle \vec{d}^*, \vec{c} \rangle$$

and using the values of \vec{d} and \vec{d}^* given by Eq.(2.22) into the last equation we get

$$L_{\vec{C}} = -\cos \theta \oint p^* dt + \sin \theta \oint q^* dt + \theta^* \left(\cos \theta \oint q dt + \sin \theta \oint p dt \right) \tag{2.65}$$

or

$$L_{\vec{C}} = -\sin \theta L_{V_1} + \cos \theta L_{V_3} + \theta^* (\cos \theta \lambda_{V_1} + \sin \theta \lambda_{V_3}) \tag{2.66}$$

Finally if we use Eq.(2.47) and Eq.(2.59) into Eq.(2.66), we get

$$L_{\vec{C}} = \sin(\varphi - \theta) L_{U_1} - \cos(\varphi - \theta) L_{U_3} + (\varphi^* - \theta^*) (\cos(\varphi - \theta) \lambda_{U_1}) + \sin(\varphi - \theta) \lambda_{U_3} \tag{2.67}$$

The dual angle of the pitch of the closed ruled surface (\vec{C}) , we may write

$$\Lambda_{\vec{C}} = -\langle \vec{D}, \vec{C} \rangle$$

and using Eq.(2.21) and Eq.(2.62) we get

$$\Lambda_{\vec{C}} = -\langle -\vec{V}_1 \oint Q dt - \vec{V}_3 \oint P dt, -\sin \Theta V_1 + \cos \Theta V_3 \rangle, \tag{2.68}$$

$$\Lambda_{\vec{C}} = -\sin \Theta \oint Q dt + \cos \Theta \oint P dt$$

If we use the Eqs.(2.45) and (2.57) into the last equation, we get

$$\Lambda_{\vec{C}} = -\sin \Theta \Lambda_{V_1} + \cos \Theta \Lambda_{V_3} \tag{2.69}$$

If we use Eq.(2.46), we get

$$\Lambda_{\vec{C}} = -\sin(\Theta - \Phi) \Lambda_{U_1} - \cos(\Theta - \Phi) \Lambda_{U_3} \tag{2.70}$$

The drall of the closed surface (\vec{C}) , we may write

$$P_{\vec{C}} = \frac{\langle d\vec{c}, d\vec{c}^* \rangle}{\langle d\vec{c}, d\vec{c} \rangle} \tag{2.71}$$

$$P_{\vec{C}} = \frac{\theta' \theta^{*'} - (q \cos \theta - p \sin \theta) [(q^* - p \theta^*) \cos \theta - (q \theta^* + p^*) \sin \theta]}{\theta'^2 - (q \cos \theta - p \sin \theta)^2}$$

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